

Supporting Information 2 – Supplementary Results

Extended results and supporting figures

Figure S1. Fossil sites grouped by European biogeographic clusters.

Figure S2. Fossil sites grouped by DBSCAN ($\epsilon = 0.02$; $\text{minPts} = 6$) clusters.

Figure S3. Fossil sites grouped into biogeographic and DBSCAN ($\epsilon = 0.02$; $\text{minPts} = 6$) clusters.

Table S3. Fossil sites, and total number of taxa binned to each space-time interval via the biogeographic clusters.

	Spatial Group (# taxa)		
	1	2	3
MIS 3	18 (59)	7 (87)	2 (26)
MIS 5	24 (89)	17 (101)	12 (98)
MIS 7	38 (119)	2 (51)	3 (33)
MIS 9	13 (85)	<u>1 (7)</u>	3 (40)
MIS 11	14 (69)	8 (82)	<u>1 (8)</u>

Note: Bold and underlined indicates omitted spatiotemporal intervals as the number of taxa is less than the minimum threshold to represent a community (<12).

Table S4. Fossil sites, and total number of taxa binned to each space-time interval via the DBSCAN clusters.

	Spatial Group (# taxa)					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
MIS 3	4 (54)	4 (53)	<u>0 (0)</u>	5 (41)	2 (26)	12 (34)
MIS 5	11 (89)	<u>1 (9)</u>	8 (61)	4 (43)	10 (89)	14 (50)
MIS 7	10 (67)	<u>0 (0)</u>	2 (51)	2 (59)	3 (33)	25 (67)
MIS 9	2 (25)	<u>0 (0)</u>	4 (44)	1 (25)	3 (40)	7 (43)
MIS 11	8 (59)	1 (22)	2 (44)	<u>1 (8)</u>	<u>0 (0)</u>	9 (53)

Note: Bold and underlined indicates omitted spatiotemporal intervals as the number of taxa is less than the minimum threshold to represent a community (<12).

Table S5. Fossil sites and total number of taxa binned to each space-time interval via the DBSCAN + Biogeographic clusters.

	Spatial Group (# taxa)						
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
MIS 3	3 (50)	4 (53)	<u>0 (0)</u>	<u>1 (11)</u>	5 (41)	12 (34)	2 (26)
MIS 5	8 (84)	<u>1 (9)</u>	8 (61)	1 (14)	4 (43)	14 (49)	10 (89)
MIS 7	<u>0 (0)</u>	<u>0 (0)</u>	2 (51)	7 (43)	2 (59)	25 (65)	3 (33)
MIS 9	<u>0 (0)</u>	<u>0 (0)</u>	<u>1 (7)</u>	2 (25)	1 (25)	7 (42)	3 (40)
MIS 11	6 (56)	1 (22)	1 (36)	<u>2 (7)</u>	<u>1 (8)</u>	9 (52)	<u>0 (0)</u>

Note: Bold and underlined indicates omitted spatiotemporal intervals as the number of taxa is less than the minimum threshold to represent a community (<12).

Figure S4. The discrete time series of community structure over marine isotope stages (MIS) under biogeographic spatial bins, highlighting the proportional representation of each guild at each space-time interval.

Figure S5. The discrete time series of community structure over marine isotope stages (MIS) under DBSCAN spatial bins, highlighting the proportional representation of each guild at each space-time interval.

Figure S6. The discrete time series of community structure over marine isotope stages (MIS) under mixed (biogeographic and DBSCAN) spatial bins, highlighting the proportional representation of each guild at each space-time interval.

Figure S7. Guild proportions per spatiotemporal interval (under biogeographic clusters) plotted against (left) number of sites per bin, and (right) number of taxa per bin. Note that large arboreal secondary consumer (LAS) and large terrestrial secondary consumer (LTS) representation decreased with number of taxa (per bin; $p < 0.10$), while small terrestrial secondary consumer (STS) representation significantly increased ($p < 0.05$).

Figure S8. Guild proportions per spatiotemporal interval (under DBSCAN clusters) plotted against (left) number of sites per bin, and (right) number of taxa per bin. Note that small arboreal primary consumer (SAP) representation decreased with number of sites (per bin; $p < 0.10$) and number of taxa (per bin; $p < 0.05$).

Figure S9. Guild proportions per spatiotemporal interval (under mixed (biogeographic and DBSCAN) clusters) plotted against (left) number of sites per bin, and (right) number of taxa per bin. Note that small arboreal primary consumer (SAP) representation decreased with number of sites (per bin; $p < 0.10$) and number of taxa (per bin; $p < 0.05$).

Figure S10. Distributions of Wilcoxon signed-rank test results from 10,000 simulated ergodic proximity arrays, based on a guild with random community representation (5 temporal intervals, 3 spatial bins). P-value distributions (A) show the distribution of 10,000 p-value outputs, and the p-values corresponding to the first, fifth and tenth percentile (corresponding to scaled $\alpha=0.01$, $\alpha=0.05$, and $\alpha=1.0$ under a uniform distribution). Effect size distributions (B) are compared from uniform random baseline, unscathed ergodic proximity inputs, and scaled ergodic proximity values standardized to the baseline's standard deviation.

Figure S11. Distributions of Wilcoxon signed-rank test results from 10,000 simulated ergodic proximity arrays, based on a guild with random community representation (5 temporal intervals, 6 spatial bins). P-value distributions (A) show the distribution of 10,000 p-value outputs, and the p-values corresponding to the first, fifth and tenth percentile (corresponding to scaled $\alpha=0.01$, $\alpha=0.05$, and $\alpha=1.0$ under a uniform distribution). Effect size distributions (B) are compared from uniform random baseline, unscaled ergodic proximity inputs, and scaled ergodic proximity values standardized to the baseline's standard deviation.

Figure S12. Distributions of Wilcoxon signed-rank test results from 10,000 simulated ergodic proximity arrays, based on a guild with random community representation (5 temporal intervals, 7 spatial bins). P-value distributions (A) show the distribution of 10,000 p-value outputs, and the p-values corresponding to the first, fifth and tenth percentile (corresponding to scaled $\alpha=0.01$, $\alpha=0.05$, and $\alpha=1.0$ under a uniform distribution). Effect size distributions (B) are compared from uniform random baseline, unscaled ergodic proximity inputs, and scaled ergodic proximity values standardized to the baseline's standard deviation.

Figure S13. Magnitude and direction of effect sizes (squares) and medians (circles) with 95% confidence intervals for each guild using the biogeographic clusters. Note dashed line at 0 on each axis representing the ergodic expectation, with *, **, and *** representing p-value significance to a thresholds of 0.10, 0.05 and 0.01 respectively.

Figure S14. Magnitude and direction of effect sizes (squares) and medians (circles) with 95% confidence intervals for each guild using the DBSCAN clusters. Note dashed line at 0 on each axis representing the ergodic expectation, with * and *** representing p-value significance to a thresholds of 0.10 and 0.01 respectively.

Figure S15. Magnitude and direction of effect sizes (squares) and medians (circles) with 95% confidence intervals for each guild using the fused (biogeographic and DBSCAN) clusters. Note dashed line at 0 on each axis representing the ergodic expectation, with ** and *** representing p-value significance to a thresholds of 0.05 and 0.01 respectively.

Figure S16. Insignificant ($p=0.8701$) correlation between evidence of ergodic processes (p -value) and guild richness using the biogeographic clustering method.

Figure S17. Insignificant ($p=0.2346$) correlation between evidence of ergodic processes (p -value) and guild richness using the DBSCAN clustering method.

Figure S18. Significant ($p < 0.05$) correlation between evidence of ergodic processes (p-value) and guild richness using the biogeographic clustering method, when omitting taxa not resolved to at least the species level.

Figure S19. Significant ($p < 0.05$) correlation between evidence of ergodic processes (p-value) and guild richness using the DBSCAN clustering method, when omitting taxa not resolved to at least the species level.

Figure S20. Insignificant correlation between evidence of ergodic processes (p-value) and guild richness using the mixed (biogeographic and DBSCAN) clustering method, when omitting taxa not resolved to at least the species level.

Figure S21. A discrete time series of large arboreal secondary consumer representation (as a proportion of total community structure, omitting taxa not resolved to the species level) across biogeographic (top), DBSCAN (middle) and mixed (bottom; biogeographic + DBSCAN) clustering methods. Note how representation drops primarily to 0 as spatial resolution increases (from top to bottom) influencing later results.

Figure S22. Significant ($p < 0.10$) correlation between evidence of ergodic processes (p-value) and guild richness using the mixed (biogeographic and DBSCAN) clustering method, when omitting taxa not resolved to at least the species level, and the large arboreal secondary consumer (an identified outlier).

Jackknife cross validation ($\alpha=0.10$, $\alpha=0.05$, $\alpha=0.01$)

Table S6. Jackknife sensitivity testing to 0.10 significance threshold.

Guild	Biogeographic			DBSCAN			Biogeographic + DBSCAN		
	H _a	H ₀	Accuracy	H _a	H ₀	Accuracy	H _a	H ₀	Accuracy
LAS	5	<u>8</u>	0.6154	11	<u>13</u>	0.5417	<u>23</u>	1	0.9583
LTP	<u>8</u>	5	0.6154	<u>13</u>	11	0.5417	<u>17</u>	7	0.7083
LTS	2	<u>11</u>	0.8462	<u>12</u>	12	0.5000	<u>18</u>	6	0.7500
SAP	<u>10</u>	3	0.7692	<u>24</u>	0	1.0000	<u>24</u>	0	1.0000
SAS	6	<u>7</u>	0.5385	6	<u>18</u>	0.7500	<u>20</u>	4	0.8333
STP	<u>12</u>	1	0.9231	6	<u>18</u>	0.7500	8	<u>16</u>	0.6667
STS	4	<u>9</u>	0.6923	3	<u>21</u>	0.8750	<u>23</u>	1	0.9583

Note: Bold and underlined figures indicate the hypothesis supported (to $\alpha=0.10$) in Table 1.

Table S7. Jackknife sensitivity testing to 0.05 significance threshold.

Guild	Biogeographic			DBSCAN			Biogeographic + DBSCAN		
	H _a	H ₀	Accuracy	H _a	H ₀	Accuracy	H _a	H ₀	Accuracy
LAS	3	<u>10</u>	0.7692	7	<u>17</u>	0.7083	<u>23</u>	1	0.9583
LTP	7	<u>6</u>	0.4615	9	<u>15</u>	0.6250	<u>15</u>	9	0.6250
LTS	1	<u>12</u>	0.9231	4	<u>20</u>	0.8333	<u>14</u>	10	0.5833
SAP	<u>8</u>	5	0.6154	<u>24</u>	0	1.0000	<u>24</u>	0	1.0000
SAS	5	<u>8</u>	0.6154	5	<u>19</u>	0.7917	<u>15</u>	9	0.6250
STP	<u>12</u>	1	0.9231	5	<u>19</u>	0.7917	1	<u>23</u>	0.9583
STS	4	<u>9</u>	0.6923	2	<u>22</u>	0.9167	<u>17</u>	7	0.7083

Note: Bold and underlined figures indicate the hypothesis supported (to $\alpha=0.05$) in Table 1.

Table S8. Jackknife sensitivity testing to 0.01 significance threshold.

Guild	Biogeographic			DBSCAN			Biogeographic + DBSCAN		
	H _a	H ₀	Accuracy	H _a	H ₀	Accuracy	H _a	H ₀	Accuracy
LAS	0	<u>13</u>	1.0000	1	<u>23</u>	0.9583	<u>23</u>	1	0.9583
LTP	4	<u>9</u>	0.6923	2	<u>22</u>	0.9167	3	<u>21</u>	0.8750
LTS	0	<u>13</u>	1.0000	1	<u>23</u>	0.9583	0	<u>24</u>	1.0000
SAP	4	<u>9</u>	0.6923	<u>24</u>	0	1.0000	<u>24</u>	0	1.0000
SAS	1	<u>12</u>	0.9231	1	<u>23</u>	0.9583	3	<u>21</u>	0.8750
STP	<u>9</u>	4	0.6923	3	<u>21</u>	0.8750	1	<u>23</u>	0.9583
STS	1	<u>12</u>	0.9231	0	<u>24</u>	1.0000	5	<u>19</u>	0.7917

Note: Bold and underlined figures indicate the hypothesis supported (to $\alpha=0.01$) in Table 1.

Additional information - primary analysis

Figure S23. Distribution of ergodic proximity inputs (per guild) for the Wilcoxon signed-rank test under biogeographic clusters.

Figure S24. Distribution of ergodic proximity inputs (per guild) for the Wilcoxon signed-rank test under DBSCAN clusters.

Figure S25. Distribution of ergodic proximity inputs (per guild) for the Wilcoxon signed-rank test under mixed (biogeographic and DBSCAN) clusters.

Additional information - extended experiment (+MIS 13/15)

We also perform our analysis on a dataset temporally extended to communities spanning MIS 13/15 (these communities could not be restricted to a single MIS), using the fused spatial binning method. This analysis provides further support to reject the null hypothesis in every guild, except small terrestrial primary consumers, with greater confidence (each effect size confidence interval spanning 0.3781) and reduced sensitivity (as per jackknife sensitivity) compared with our principal model.

Figure S26. Fossil sites grouped into biogeographic and DBSCAN ($\epsilon = 0.02$; $\text{minPts} = 6$) clusters under the extended (+MIS 13/15) experiment.

Table S9. Fossil sites and total number of taxa binned to each space-time interval via the DBSCAN + Biogeographic clusters up to MIS 13/15.

	Spatial Group (# taxa)						
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
MIS 3	3 (50)	4 (53)	<u>0 (0)</u>	<u>1 (11)</u>	5 (41)	12 (34)	2 (26)
MIS 5	8 (84)	<u>1 (9)</u>	8 (61)	1 (14)	4 (43)	14 (49)	11 (89)
MIS 7	<u>0 (0)</u>	<u>0 (0)</u>	2 (51)	7 (43)	2 (59)	25 (65)	3 (33)
MIS 9	<u>0 (0)</u>	<u>0 (0)</u>	<u>1 (7)</u>	2 (25)	1 (25)	7 (42)	3 (40)
MIS 11	6 (56)	1 (22)	1 (36)	<u>2 (7)</u>	<u>1 (8)</u>	9 (52)	<u>0 (0)</u>
MIS 13/15	8 (126)	<u>0 (0)</u>	<u>0 (0)</u>	1 (28)	<u>0 (0)</u>	7 (61)	4 (43)

Note: Bold and underlined indicates omitted spatiotemporal intervals as the number of taxa is less than the minimum threshold to represent a community (<12).

Figure S27. Distributions of Wilcoxon signed-rank test results from 10,000 simulated ergodic proximity arrays, based on a guild with random community representation (6 temporal intervals, 7 spatial bins). P-value distributions (A) show the distribution of 10,000 p-value outputs, and the p-values corresponding to the first, fifth and tenth percentile (corresponding to scaled $\alpha=0.01$, $\alpha=0.05$, and $\alpha=1.0$ under a uniform distribution). Effect size distributions (B) are compared from uniform random baseline, unscaled ergodic proximity inputs, and scaled ergodic proximity values standardized to the baseline's standard deviation.

Figure S28. The discrete time series of community structure over marine isotope stages (MIS) under mixed (biogeographic and DBSCAN) spatial bins in the extended (+MIS 13/15) experiment, highlighting the proportional representation of each guild at each space-time interval.

Figure S29. Distribution of ergodic proximity inputs (per guild) for the Wilcoxon signed-rank test under mixed (biogeographic and DBSCAN) clusters in the extended experiment (+MIS 13/15).

Figure S30. Guild proportions per spatiotemporal interval (under DBSCAN clusters in the extended (+MIS 13/15) experiment) plotted against (left) number of sites per bin, and (right) number of taxa per bin. Note that small arboreal primary consumer (SAP) representation decreased with number of sites (per bin; $p < 0.10$).

Table S10. Outputs of Wilcoxon signed rank tests on ergodic proximities for the extended (+MIS 13/15) experiment.

Guild	n	t-stat	Median (90% CI)	Effect Size (90% CI) Scaled¹ Effect Size (90% CI)	p-value	Sig²
LAS	13	319	-0.0079 (-0.0085, -0.0072)	-0.2935 (-0.3546, -0.2540) -1.1360 (-1.3727, -0.9832)	0.0992	***
LTP	75	366	-0.0203 (-0.0209, -0.0198)	-0.1894 (-0.2445, -0.1455) -0.7330 (-0.9464, -0.5632)	0.2911	***
LTS	33	410	-0.0026 (-0.0028, -0.0023)	-0.0919 (-0.1410, -0.0411) -0.3558 (-0.5458, -0.1591)	0.6117	**
SAP	9	286	-0.0046 (-0.0063, -0.0029)	-0.3666 (-0.4159, -0.3259) -1.4189 (-1.6101, -1.2617)	0.0382	***
SAS	56	368	0.0159 (0.0109, 0.0209)	0.1849 (0.1374, 0.2342) 0.7159 (0.5318, 0.9066)	0.3027	***
STP	54	431	0.0123 (0.0106, 0.0140)	0.0454 (-0.0032, 0.0973) 0.1758 (-0.0125, 0.3765)	0.8045	
STS	40	383	-0.0024 (-0.0025, -0.0021)	0.1517 (0.1015, 0.1983) 0.5873 (0.3928, 0.7677)	0.3991	***

Note: (¹) Effect scaling factor: 3.8710; (²) Significance thresholds (Sig.), **($\alpha=0.05 \rightarrow 0.6123$), ***($\alpha=0.01 \rightarrow 0.4091$)

Figure S31. Magnitude and direction of effect sizes (squares) and medians (circles) with 95% confidence intervals for each guild using the fused (biogeographic and DBSCAN) clusters in the extended (+MIS 13/15) experiment. Note dashed line at 0 on each axis representing the ergodic expectation, with ** and *** representing p-value significance to a thresholds of 0.05 and 0.01 respectively.

Table S11. Outputs of Jackknife cross validation on the extended (MIS 3-13/15) experiment under fused (biogeographic + DBSCAN) clusters.

Guild	$\alpha=0.10$			$\alpha=0.05$			$\alpha=0.01$		
	H _a	H ₀	Accuracy	H _a	H ₀	Accuracy	H _a	H ₀	Accuracy
LAS	<u>28</u>	0	1.0000	<u>28</u>	0	1.0000	<u>27</u>	1	0.9643
LTP	<u>28</u>	0	1.0000	<u>27</u>	1	0.9643	<u>21</u>	7	0.7500
LTS	<u>24</u>	4	0.8571	<u>17</u>	11	0.6071	4	<u>24</u>	0.8571
SAP	<u>27</u>	1	0.9643	<u>27</u>	1	0.9643	<u>27</u>	1	0.9643
SAS	<u>28</u>	0	1.0000	<u>28</u>	0	1.0000	<u>22</u>	6	0.7857
STP	8	<u>20</u>	0.7143	4	<u>24</u>	0.8571	1	<u>27</u>	0.9643
STS	<u>28</u>	0	1.0000	<u>27</u>	1	0.9643	<u>11</u>	17	0.3929

Note: Bold and underlined figures indicate the hypothesis supported in Table S10.

Figure 32. Insignificant ($p=0.2906$) correlation between evidence of ergodic processes (p -value) and guild richness using the mixed (biogeographic and DBSCAN) clustering method in the extended (+MIS 13/15) experiment.

Additional information - species-resolved taxon only

These selected results highlight differences between our primary experiments (outlined in the main manuscript and extended results) and then these same experiments repeated with only taxa resolved to the species level. Any taxa identified coarser than the species level (including species-complexes) have been omitted from these trials.

Note that in this test, using biogeographic analysis, small terrestrial secondary consumers are shown to negatively accumulate with increased taxonomic sampling ($p < 0.05$). Furthermore, small terrestrial primary consumers are shown to negatively accumulate with increased site representation in this test's DBSCAN analysis ($p < 0.05$) and mixed analysis ($s(p < 0.10)$).

Table S12. Fossil sites, and total number of taxa (resolved to the species level) binned to each space-time interval via the biogeographic clusters.

	Spatial Group (# taxa)		
	1	2	3
MIS 3	18 (27)	7 (42)	2 (13)
MIS 5	24 (39)	17 (49)	12 (46)
MIS 7	38 (55)	2 (24)	3 (14)
MIS 9	13 (34)	<u>1 (0)</u>	3 (14)
MIS 11	14 (30)	8 (35)	<u>1 (0)</u>

Note: Bold and underlined indicates omitted spatiotemporal intervals as the number of taxa is less than the minimum threshold to represent a community (<12).

Table S13 Fossil sites, and total number of taxa (resolved to the species level) binned to each space-time interval via the DBSCAN clusters.

	Spatial Group (# taxa)					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
MIS 3	4 (26)	4 (27)	<u>0 (0)</u>	5 (21)	2 (13)	12 (13)
MIS 5	11 (41)	<u>1 (3)</u>	8 (27)	4 (28)	10 (40)	14 (15)
MIS 7	10 (26)	<u>0 (0)</u>	2 (24)	2 (44)	3 (14)	25 (28)
MIS 9	<u>2 (7)</u>	<u>0 (0)</u>	4 (18)	1 (14)	3 (14)	7 (15)
MIS 11	8 (19)	1 (14)	2 (18)	<u>1 (8)</u>	<u>0 (0)</u>	9 (22)

Note: Bold and underlined indicates omitted spatiotemporal intervals as the number of taxa is less than the minimum threshold to represent a community (<12).

Table S14. Fossil sites and total number of taxa (resolved to the species level) binned to each space-time interval via the mixed (DBSCAN + Biogeographic) clusters.

	Spatial Group (# taxa)						
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
MIS 3	3 (25)	4 (27)	<u>0 (0)</u>	<u>1 (3)</u>	5 (21)	12 (13)	2 (13)
MIS 5	8 (40)	<u>1 (3)</u>	8 (27)	<u>1 (7)</u>	4 (28)	14 (15)	10 (40)
MIS 7	<u>0 (0)</u>	<u>0 (0)</u>	2 (24)	<u>7 (7)</u>	2 (44)	25 (28)	3 (14)
MIS 9	<u>0 (0)</u>	<u>0 (0)</u>	<u>1 (0)</u>	<u>2 (7)</u>	1 (14)	7 (15)	3 (14)
MIS 11	6 (19)	1 (14)	1 (16)	<u>2 (1)</u>	<u>1 (8)</u>	9 (22)	<u>0 (0)</u>

Note: Bold and underlined indicates omitted spatiotemporal intervals as the number of taxa is less than the minimum threshold to represent a community (<12).

Table S15. Outputs of Wilcoxon signed rank tests on ergodic proximities (for taxa resolved at least to the species level).

Biogeographic tests						
Guild	n	t-stat	Median (90% CI)	Effect Size (90% CI) Scaled¹ Effect Size (90% CI)	p-value	Sig²
LAS	9	41	-0.0078 (-0.0201, 0.0044)	-0.2190 (-0.3891, -0.0628) -0.9135 (-1.6226, -0.2619)	0.5016	**
LTP	50	57	0.0056 (0.0019, 0.0070)	0.0500 (-0.0906, 0.2252) 0.2085 (-0.3778, 0.9393)	0.8904	
LTS	23	41	-0.0148 (-0.0326, 0.0290)	0.3167 (0.1702, 0.4503) 1.3206 (0.7098, 1.8780)	0.3028	***
SAP	7	42	-0.0033 (-0.0047, 0.0001)	-0.3000 (-0.4553, -0.1615) -1.2511 (-1.8989, -0.6736)	0.3303	***
SAS	40	52	-0.0100 (-0.0187, -0.0018)	-0.1333 (-0.3064, 0.0075) -0.5561 (-1.2777, 0.0314)	0.6788	*
STP	36	55	-0.0024 (-0.0084, 0.0032)	0.0833 (-0.0839, 0.2260) 0.3475 (-0.3497, 0.9424)	0.804	
STS	26	47	-0.0044 (-0.0114, 0.0031)	-0.2167 (-0.3618, -0.0647) -0.9036 (-1.5089, -0.2698)	0.4887	**
DBSCAN tests						
Guild	n	t-stat	Median (90% CI)	Effect Size (90% CI) Scaled³ Effect Size (90% CI)	p-value	Sig⁴
LAS	9	127	-0.0060 (-0.0219, 0.0003)	-0.3280 (-0.4143, -0.2608) -1.3530 (-1.7089, -1.0757)	0.1414	***
LTP	50	197	-0.0265 (-0.0297, -0.0233)	-0.1527 (-0.2362, -0.0902) -0.6298 (-0.9743, -0.3719)	0.4771	**
LTS	23	209	-0.0183 (-0.0258, -0.0107)	-0.1011 (-0.1804, -0.0360) -0.4169 (-0.7441, -0.1487)	0.6408	*
SAP	7	100	-0.0116 (-0.0141, -0.0105)	-0.5402 (-0.6015, -0.4884) -2.2282 (-2.4811, -2.0144)	0.0099	***
SAS	40	216	0.0022 (-0.0046, 0.0090)	0.0710 (0.0006, 0.1444) 0.2927 (0.0024, 0.5956)	0.7457	
STP	36	211	0.0065 (0.0044, 0.0085)	0.0925 (0.0206, 0.1636) 0.3814 (0.0851, 0.6747)	0.6702	*
STS	26	187	0.0023 (-0.0082, 0.0127)	-0.1957 (-0.2598, -0.1232) -0.8072 (-1.0714, -0.5082)	0.3599	***

Biogeographic + DBSCAN tests

Guild	n	t-stat	Median (90% CI)	Effect Size (90% CI) Scaled ⁵ Effect Size (90% CI)	p-value	Sig ⁶
LAS	9	144	0.0000 (-0.0022, 0.0022)	-0.0400 (-0.1368, 0.0478) -0.1576 (-0.5389, 0.1885)	0.8774	
LTP	50	191	-0.0451 (-0.0535, -0.0367)	-0.1785 (-0.2585, -0.1138) -0.7031 (-1.0182, -0.4481)	0.4045	***
LTS	23	176	-0.0263 (-0.0309, -0.0217)	-0.2430 (-0.3185, -0.1789) -0.9572 (-1.2545, -0.7045)	0.2534	***
SAP	7	108	-0.0119 (-0.0127, -0.0098)	-0.5034 (-0.5700, -0.4491) -1.9830 (-2.2451, -1.7690)	0.0168	***
SAS	40	208	0.0021 (-0.0076, 0.0118)	0.1054 (0.0332, 0.1749) 0.4151 (0.1310, 0.6891)	0.6263	*
STP	36	217	0.0052 (0.0014, 0.0090)	0.0667 (-0.0031, 0.1406) 0.2626 (-0.0121, 0.5540)	0.7611	
STS	26	186	-0.0044 (-0.0087, -0.0001)	-0.2000 (-0.2662, -0.1291) -0.7878 (-1.0486, -0.5083)	0.3492	***

Note: (1) Effect scaling factor: 4.1704; (2) Significance thresholds (Sig.), *($\alpha=0.1 \rightarrow 0.7437$), **($\alpha=0.05 \rightarrow 0.6451$), ***($\alpha=0.01 \rightarrow 0.4293$); (3) Effect scaling factor: 4.1246; (4) Significance thresholds (Sig.), *($\alpha=0.10 \rightarrow 0.7169$), **($\alpha=0.05 \rightarrow 0.6375$), ***($\alpha=0.01 \rightarrow 0.4365$); (5) Effect scaling factor: 3.9388; (6) Significance thresholds (Sig.), *($\alpha=0.1 \rightarrow 0.7029$), ***($\alpha=0.01 \rightarrow 0.4118$)

Table S16. Jackknife sensitivity testing to 0.10 significance threshold (only using taxa resolved to the species level).

Guild	Biogeographic			DBSCAN			Biogeographic + DBSCAN		
	H _a	H ₀	Accuracy	H _a	H ₀	Accuracy	H _a	H ₀	Accuracy
LAS	<u>11</u>	2	0.8462	<u>20</u>	3	0.8696	4	<u>17</u>	0.8095
LTP	2	<u>11</u>	0.8462	<u>23</u>	0	1.0000	<u>21</u>	0	1.0000
LTS	<u>13</u>	0	1.0000	<u>14</u>	9	0.6087	<u>21</u>	0	1.0000
SAP	<u>12</u>	1	0.9231	<u>23</u>	0	1.0000	<u>21</u>	0	1.0000
SAS	<u>8</u>	5	0.6154	9	<u>14</u>	0.6087	<u>15</u>	6	0.7143
STP	5	<u>8</u>	0.6154	<u>13</u>	10	0.5652	11	<u>10</u>	0.4762
STS	<u>12</u>	1	0.9231	<u>23</u>	0	1.0000	<u>20</u>	1	0.9524

Note: Bold and underlined figures indicate the hypothesis supported (to $\alpha=0.10$) in Table S15.

Table S17. Jackknife sensitivity testing to 0.05 significance threshold (only using taxa resolved to the species level).

Guild	Biogeographic			DBSCAN			Biogeographic + DBSCAN		
	H _a	H ₀	Accuracy	H _a	H ₀	Accuracy	H _a	H ₀	Accuracy
LAS	<u>11</u>	2	0.8462	<u>20</u>	3	0.8696	4	<u>17</u>	0.8095
LTP	1	<u>12</u>	0.9231	<u>22</u>	1	0.9565	<u>21</u>	0	1.0000
LTS	<u>11</u>	2	0.8462	9	<u>14</u>	0.6087	<u>21</u>	0	1.0000
SAP	<u>11</u>	2	0.8462	<u>22</u>	1	0.9565	<u>21</u>	0	1.0000
SAS	7	<u>6</u>	0.4615	8	<u>15</u>	0.6522	12	<u>9</u>	0.4286
STP	5	<u>8</u>	0.6154	8	<u>15</u>	0.6522	9	<u>12</u>	0.5714
STS	<u>11</u>	2	0.8462	<u>23</u>	0	1.0000	<u>20</u>	1	0.9524

Note: Bold and underlined figures indicate the hypothesis supported (to $\alpha=0.05$) in Table S15.

Table S18. Jackknife sensitivity testing to 0.01 significance threshold (only using taxa resolved to the species level).

Guild	Biogeographic			DBSCAN			Biogeographic + DBSCAN		
	H _a	H ₀	Accuracy	H _a	H ₀	Accuracy	H _a	H ₀	Accuracy
LAS	1	<u>12</u>	0.9231	<u>20</u>	3	0.8696	4	<u>17</u>	0.8095
LTP	0	<u>13</u>	1.0000	8	<u>15</u>	0.6522	<u>11</u>	10	0.5238
LTS	<u>10</u>	3	0.7692	1	<u>22</u>	0.9565	<u>20</u>	1	0.9524
SAP	<u>9</u>	4	0.6923	<u>22</u>	1	0.9565	<u>20</u>	1	0.9524
SAS	5	<u>8</u>	0.6154	0	<u>23</u>	1.0000	4	<u>17</u>	0.8095
STP	1	<u>12</u>	0.9231	2	<u>21</u>	0.9130	3	<u>18</u>	0.8571
STS	7	<u>6</u>	0.4615	<u>18</u>	5	0.7826	<u>15</u>	6	0.7143

Note: Bold and underlined figures indicate the hypothesis supported (to $\alpha=0.01$) in Table S15.